

Experiment Design for Data Science

Simple And Efficient Recommendation Strategy For Warm/Cold Sessions For Recsys Challenge 2022

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Group 02

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Introduction

The RecSys 2022 Challenge organized by Dressipi aimed to tackle the complex problem of predicting the next item a user is likely to purchase based on their session data and item metadata from a fashion e-commerce service. The challenge of this problem was due to the limited information available in most user sessions, which often only had a few previous views, and the presence of unfamiliar items in many sessions, both in terms of view number, view date, view sequence as well as purchase number, purchase sequence and purchases.

To overcome these obstacles, the authors proposed a novel approach that included a sequence-aware multi-layer perceptron (MLP) model, which outperformed other sequential recommenders such as BERT4Rec and GRU4Rec. The approach also involved a unique similarity metric that considered both item metadata and popularity, as well as a recommendation prediction strategy that utilized different serving models for different types of sessions. This innovative approach enabled the authors to effectively predict the next item a user was likely to purchase and demonstrate the utility of the proposed approach in real-world applications. The results of the challenge demonstrate the potential of these techniques in improving the accuracy of recommendations and providing a better user experience.

Methodology

The approach used in this study is an ensemble of multiple models. Ensemble algorithms are machine learning techniques that combine the predictions of multiple individual models in order to improve the overall performance of the system. The idea behind ensemble methods is that by combining the strengths of multiple predictors, the weaknesses of each individual model can be mitigated, leading to a more robust and accurate overall prediction and by combining the predictions of multiple accurate models, it can be achieved a higher level of performance compared to using a single model. This is because the weaknesses of individual models are balanced out by the strengths of others, leading to a more robust and accurate overall prediction. By utilizing ensemble techniques, it is possible to attain a few more percent points in terms of the required metric, making it a desirable approach in recommender system applications.

The overall architecture of the system is depicted in Figure 1. The input session is first classified based on the proportion of "cold" items present in the session, where an item is considered "cold" if it did not appear in the previous 3 months. If the session has a

low percentage (less than 70%) of cold items, recommendations are generated by combining the outputs of several session-based models, including the Sequence-Aware MLP (SMLP), GRU4Rec, BERT4Rec and Popularity-Aware Cosine Similarity (PCos).

However, if the session contains a high percentage of cold items, recommendations are generated using the proposed item metadata similarity metric, PCos. This ensemble approach allows them to leverage the strengths of multiple models and provide more accurate and diverse recommendations.

Fig 1. Proposed Method

Reproducibility

We initially began by thoroughly reviewing the literature and understanding the key concepts presented in the paper. Afterwards, we examined the accompanying Github repository to gain insight into the implementation of the models. Upon examination, we observed that the authors had utilized several new models in their approach, specifically Graph Neural Networks (GNN), GRU, GRU_all and a combination model utilizing both GRU and GNN which had the name GRUN.

In order to start training the model one needs to perform preprocessing as described in the paper. With this step we did not encounter any problems and it can be performed with the following line: `python preprocessing.py --submit=True`. If we set `--submit=True`, we build preprocessed for the leaderboard (and final).

After this step is done one can train GRU, GRUN and GNN models with the following command: `!bash /content/kakao-recoteam-recsys-2022-challenge/run.sh`.

We encountered limitations while running the full ensemble model as per the original plan. One of the major challenges we faced was related to the computational requirements of the GRU-GRUN-GNN model. Training process is made of 20 iterations where for each iteration GRU, GRUN and GNN models are trained respectively, for training the authors used 30-50 epochs (GNN had 50 epochs and GRU had 30 epochs). The training process of this model was extremely time-consuming and required a large amount of computational resources. Despite our efforts to reduce the number of iterations in order to speed up the training process, we were unable to fully train this model. Once we changed the number of iterations just to one, the training process still took 10 hours to finish and after it was done we managed to generate recommendations for these models. The calculation of cosine similarity "Pcos" was also performed with the following command: `!python module/models/ensemble.py --fork_fallback=True --submit=True --kind=final`. Which means that we are creating recommendations for final sessions.

The next step in order to obtain final results was to run the BERT4Rec model. But in order to run this model authors noted that we should install their BERT4Rec implementation with the following command:

```
!python /content/kakao-recoteam-recsys-2022-challenge/BERT4Rec/setup.py install
```

But unfortunately, an unexpected issue arose with the BERT4Rec model, which is a crucial component of the ensemble model. Despite the files being present in the system, it was missing a necessary file that prevented us from including this model in the ensemble. As a result we couldn't train the ensemble model. The error we got is presented in figure 2:

```
!python /content/kakao-recoteam-recsys-2022-challenge/BERT4Rec/setup.py install
```

```
Traceback (most recent call last):
  File "/content/kakao-recoteam-recsys-2022-challenge/BERT4Rec/setup.py", line 25, in <module>
    ext_modules=cythonize(ext_modules),
  File "/usr/local/lib/python3.8/dist-packages/Cython/Build/Dependencies.py", line 970, in cythonize
    module_list, module_metadata = create_extension_list(
  File "/usr/local/lib/python3.8/dist-packages/Cython/Build/Dependencies.py", line 816, in create_extension_list
    for file in nonempty(sorted(extended_iglob(filepattern)), "'%s' doesn't match any files" % filepattern):
  File "/usr/local/lib/python3.8/dist-packages/Cython/Build/Dependencies.py", line 114, in nonempty
    raise ValueError(error_msg)
ValueError: 'bert4rec/data/c_mr.pyx' doesn't match any files
```

Fig 2. BERT4Rec error

Metrics

In this study, the authors have chosen two evaluation metrics to assess the performance of their model: MRR@100 and HIT. HIT is used for training, while MRR@100 is used to measure the effectiveness of the retrieval system. MRR stands for Mean Reciprocal Rank and it calculates the reciprocal of the rank of the first relevant item in the returned results. This measure is used to emphasize the importance of ranking relevant items at the top of the list and de-emphasize the ranking of relevant items at the bottom. MRR is commonly used in information retrieval research to compare the performance of different retrieval models or algorithms.

Conclusion

In our research, we attempted to reproduce a previously published paper with ensemble algorithms. However, we encountered a major obstacle as the hardware specifications on which the original study was conducted were not provided in the paper. This lack of information made it difficult for us to accurately replicate the results and compare our findings.

Despite this, we made attempts to run the ensemble algorithms on various platforms, including our laptops, M1 Pro Mac, laptops with Nvidia GPU, Google Colab, and Google Colab Pro and a high-performance workstation with an Intel i9 processor and Nvidia 3090 RTX graphics card. Despite the advantage of having more resources on Google Colab Pro and the powerful workstation, the program still timed out after 24 hours, much like our access to the workstation. The limited amount of time on both platforms did not provide us with enough resources to complete the full replication of the study. Despite these challenges, we believe that the proper documentation of hardware specifications is crucial for the reproducibility of research results and should be included in all publications.

During the training step we were provided with MRR@100 and HIT for each epoch while training. We have obtained the following results (using one iteration only) regarding the GRU, GRUN, GNN and GRU_all models:

	HIT	MRR	LOSS
GRUN_all	0.620000	0.23291093	5.68048638203105
GRUN	0.614000	0.23088220	5.24437589256476
GNN	0.609000	0.20749533	5.766059416687517
GRU	0.583000	0.23594540	5.245073761641275

